

1. Project Summary

Title of the project:	Machine learning infrastructure deployed at scale: understanding requirements, demand, impact and international best practice.
Lead organisation / contractor:	MASSIVE (Monash University)
Project leader:	Wojtek James Goscinski, Komathy Padmanabhan
Other organisations involved:	Monash University, Research Computing Centre (RCC) at The University of Queensland, Alfred Health, Victorian Institute for Forensic Medicine, University of Auckland, NVIDIA

ARDC question the project addressed:

DAP/T5/P8: What is the demand for machine learning tools and services and how could these be most effectively supported?

Executive Summary

The authors have undertaken a major review of the research development and application of Machine Learning (ML). The following is a summary of our findings and our resulting recommendations.

	Research Finding	Infrastructure Recommendation
Relevance and Growth	<p>We identified 128 research groups across three Universities that apply or develop ML techniques. Of the identified research groups, 68 completed the survey (53% response rate).</p> <p>The community is growing quickly as acknowledged by all three sites: MASSIVE at Monash, University of Queensland and University of Auckland .</p>	<p>There is a strong and growing appetite across research groups for access to ML capacity, services, libraries, expertise and training.</p>
Capacity and Hardware	<p>Researchers use a range of capabilities to undertake ML. 63% of researchers use HPC facilities to access GPU capability. 19% use commercial clouds. The main consideration with commercial clouds the cost and integration with other infrastructure.</p> <p>62% of researchers are found to use their local desktop for building and testing</p>	<p>Infrastructure providers should collaborate nationally to increase the overall pool of available resources. HPC centres offering significant GPU capacity are important to this effort as they represent the majority of available GPU capacity for research in Australia and are the primary support contact.</p> <p>Increase knowledge to improve efficiency of</p>

	<p>models on small data before progressing to greater processing and validation using HPC or central servers with large datasets.</p> <p>Current computing capacity is highly inadequate with requirements growing quickly.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 68% of the researchers expect that their compute needs to grow by 100%-200% in the next year. 15% expect that their computing needs will grow by over 200%. 54% of the researchers indicate that compute capacity is their major challenge. <p>It is estimated that the 128 projects identified currently 3,008,802 GPU hours per annum, or an equivalent of 125 GPUs.</p>	<p>usage.</p> <p>Provide knowledge, training and test environments to allow researchers to test ideas, demonstrate success and potentially fail quickly.</p> <p>Develop investment and access models to allow national access to GPU computing.</p> <p>Increase system administrator knowledge on how to deploy and configure libraries efficiently and effectively to best leverage the limited hardware available.</p>
Techniques and Environments	<p>Neural networks & Deep Learning (79%) and Linear regression (32%) are the most commonly used ML techniques.</p> <p>Tensorflow, Keras, Pytorch, scikit-learn, Pytorch and Caffe are the most widely used ML tools/libraries/frameworks.</p> <p>Pandas for Python, Matlab and Moa are used widely for data manipulation, mining and analysis.</p> <p>Currently researchers must move between environments to develop, train and test. This includes their personal desktop PC, HPC systems, clouds and storage.</p>	<p>The focus on key libraries such as Tensorflow, Pytorch and Caffe is an opportunity to develop and spread detailed knowledge across a wide variety of research challenges. It means a large number of researchers can be assisted by providing expertise across a small number of tools/libraries/frameworks.</p> <p>Create integrated infrastructure that allow researchers to access interactive development environments, interactive compute for testing training, heavier compute for dedicated training, data manipulation tools, and access to data, in an efficient and integrated manner.</p>
Data	<p>Availability & accessibility of quality big data is a challenge for more than 50% of the researchers surveyed. Limited availability of annotated/labelled datasets means researchers spend a lot of time and effort pre-processing data.</p> <p>A key highlight is the sensitivity of the data & privacy issues associated with it. 53% of the researchers indicated that their data is sensitive and needs to be secured and managed appropriately.</p> <p>A large proportion (73%) of the researchers use public reference datasets for training, testing and benchmarking their models.</p>	<p>Provide access to existing curated and well annotated data repositories for ML adopters and practitioners. Provide access to this data on ML hardware.</p> <p>Integrate ML capability with the appropriate controls to host sensitive data to underpin the 50%+ of researchers who require strong data security and governance.</p> <p>Curate and make available reference data sets commonly used by ML practitioners as a standard offering across GPU computing facilities.</p>
Knowledge and Training	<p>The lack of researchers with machine learning skills and domain expertise is seen</p>	<p>Provide targeted training programs & hands on workshops to ML developer cohorts and</p>

	<p>as one of the key challenges in applying ML to research.</p> <p>Training needs are found to be different for ML researchers who develop algorithms and ML researchers who apply ML to their research.</p> <p>Understandably, training needs are also found to be different for researchers with different expertise levels.</p>	<p>applied ML researcher cohorts.</p> <p>Provide training on research specific tools and IDEs like NVIDIA Clara for Healthcare researchers, PyTorch for computer vision and NLP researchers.</p>
<p>Community</p>	<p>The ML user community can be classified into three main cohorts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Researchers who develop new ML algorithms and apply these new techniques to new domains (47%) ● Researchers who are primarily applying existing algorithms and libraries to their research challenge (46%), and ● Researchers who are actively seeking opportunities to apply ML techniques but have not started yet(7%). <p>90% of ML researchers are multidisciplinary and have active collaborations to solve real and practical research questions that has social impact.</p> <p>Researchers who primarily develop ML techniques are most likely to have collaborations in: computer vision, natural language processing, Neural Networks and Deep Learning.</p> <p>Researchers who primarily apply ML techniques are most likely to have collaborations in: neuroscience, radiology, engineering, smart city, law and robotics.</p> <p>Significant industry partnerships were identified.</p>	<p>Promote ML as a major tool for multidisciplinary research</p> <p>Build specific national communities of practise in the identified areas by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Developing and promoting forums and exchange of ideas, ● Targeted training, ● Regular remote hybrid training. <p>Underpin collaborations with key international programs that would align well with Australian interests:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● US DOE programs to develop ML generated scientific solvers and numerical kernels. ● CCDS for cross training radiology ML models across different sites. ● UCSD for development environments. <p>Leverage appetite for industry partnerships by supporting existing partnerships and building new partnerships.</p>

2. Project Goal

Over the past two years, we have identified a steep increase in the application of machine learning (ML) techniques, across a wide range of domains, including neuroscience, economic sciences & econometrics, image processing, engineering, security, biological sciences, law, education, and translational health. Our research platforms, MASSIVE and UQ RCC, have seen a significant increase in demand for hardware suited to deep learning, including GPUs and high-bandwidth file systems.

This report is the outcome of the study we undertook to investigate the soft and hard infrastructure required to underpin and support the increasing adoption of ML, at scale. Our goals for the study were:

1. To form a clear understanding of the relationship between research requirements, computing capability, capacity, and research impact. We aimed to address this goal across a range of researchers and institution-wide.
2. To understand individual researcher requirements and consolidate these across a large cohort of groups, so that we can make evidence-based recommendations on how to underpin research adopting ML in the most efficient and effective manner, at scale.
3. To understand international best practices, and how it should inform Australian investment.

This study focussed on current and foreseeable requirements, challenges, current demand for capacity, future growth and impact, across groups applying ML to their research, and groups developing applied ML techniques.

3. Approach

The information and recommendations presented in this report were developed using the data collected through surveys and interactions with exemplar facilities, as outlined below.

3.1.1 Survey & Interviews with Researchers

1. We developed a comprehensive researcher survey that addressed a range of quantitative and qualitative questions. These questions addressed the following areas:
 - General information to identify the institution, research domain, ML expertise, intended purpose of applying ML techniques and the impact of ML on research.
 - Tools and techniques being used.
 - Computing infrastructure being adopted, including HPC, GPU hardware, and the capacity required. This includes specific questions on the application of the commercial cloud.
 - Data that is being processed and the sensitivity of this data.
 - Skills and training requirements to help with adoption, growth and to increase research quality.
 - General and specific challenges in applying ML.

This survey was tested on a small number of researchers in an interview format before being sent out to the whole cohort of researcher groups. This approach allowed us to refine question wording and identify additional pertinent questions from a semi-structured interview. The questions were targeted at research group leaders, and they were requested to answer questions on behalf of the overall research group.

2. We identified 128 research groups across Monash University, University of Queensland, University of Auckland, and users of facilities hosted by these three institutions. This list was created as a combination of project lists from HPC and cloud facilities and known research

projects by University eResearch Centres. Of the identified research groups, 68 completed the survey (53% response rate).

3. As a token of thanks for participation, a lucky draw has been conducted and Qantas flight vouchers valued \$250 have been awarded to 3 lucky participants.

3.1.2 Interviews with International Exemplar facilities

In order to understand the International Best Practices, we conducted a number of unstructured interviews with International facilities, in collaboration with other ARDC discovery project - Global Experiences - Digital Research Infrastructure Federations. The interviews focussed on goals, challenges, successes, operations and learnings of the Exemplar facilities. The information gathered from these meetings informed our Recommendations.

Facilities interviewed were

- Centre for Clinical Data science, Partners Health, Boston
- University of Michigan Advanced Research Computing & Michigan Institute of Data science
- Jetstream at Indiana University
- Cambridge University Research computing
- European organisation for Nuclear Research - CERN

4. Findings

4.1. Findings from Survey & Interviews with Researchers

Researchers across almost all fields of research are seen to adopting Machine Learning to their research. More than half of the researchers (51%) were applying ML to **build smarter systems that can interact better with the world**, extract more insightful information or building systems that are faster and more efficient than the existing ones.

Fig 4.1.1 Reason for applying ML to research

46% of the researchers identified themselves as experts and 40% of them identified themselves having intermediate skills in ML. 84% of the researchers claim that most members of their research group are either proficient or on their way to being proficient.

Fig 4.1.2 Expertise in Machine Learning

Significantly large cohort of researchers (89%) were applying existing ML algorithms and techniques to their research.

4.1.1 Field of Research

Information and computer science researchers (35.8%), Medical & Health sciences (14.2%) and Engineering researchers (10.4%) are the three large research disciplines, developing and applying ML to their research. A small 6% of HASS researchers are seen to apply ML in the areas of economics, commerce and management.

Fig 4.1.3 Field of Research applying ML

4.1.2 Methods, techniques and tools

77% of the researchers used supervised learning methods in their research. Unsupervised learning (51%), semi-supervised learning (37%) and Reinforcement Learning (25%) are other highly used methods.

Neural networks & Deep Learning (79%) and Linear regression (32%) are the most commonly used techniques. Other techniques applied largely are Support vector Machines, Decision trees and K-means clustering.

Tensorflow, Keras, Pytorch, scikit-learn, Pytorch and Caffe are the most widely used tools/libraries/frameworks used for Machine learning. **Pandas for Python, Matlab and Moe** are used widely for data manipulation, mining and analysis.

iPython Notebooks (40%) followed by Rstudio (19%) and JupyterHub (14%) are the most common interactive computational and development environments, used by the researchers.

4.1.3 Stages and efforts

On an average, researchers spend 17% of their time for data collection, 23% on data pre-processing activities (wrangling, cleanup and transformation), 36% on Model development and 24% on model validation.

Fig 4.1.4 Average percentage of time spent on ML activities by ML Researchers

Fig 4.1.4 Average percentage of time spent on ML activities by Applied ML Researchers

There is a very high variation of the proportion of time spent on each stage by the researchers. For example, researchers have indicated that they spend between 15 and 55% of their time developing models.

4.1.4 Challenges

Having appropriate Machine Learning skills with relevant domain knowledge (34%) within their research group is the key challenge that researchers face for applying Machine Learning in their research.

Fig 4.1.5 Current challenges in applying ML

Capacity of the hardware (32%) and Data availability & accessibility (29%) are the other challenges. Infrastructure capacity, Lack of sufficient quality data, Time intensive nature of data pre-processing, Lack of appropriately skilled staff and Insufficient staff capacity are the current major barriers for applying Machine Learning to the research.

4.1.5 Impact

Most of the researchers (76%) see that Machine Learning is the **crucial enabler to accelerate research and enable new and faster discoveries**, which wouldn't have been possible earlier, specifically in image processing, genetic sequencing and analysing 3D structures.

Complex decision management & benchmarking systems, accurate prediction models, remote sensing etc. in real time are the key application of machine learning in various areas of research.

AI for Social good is found to be the most impactful theme among the researchers and is largely prevalent in Improving healthcare, but is applied across various other sectors like sustainability (Recycling, study of vegetation etc.), economic development, defense & security, Smart cities etc.

4.2 Interviews with International Exemplar Facilities

Discussions major international sites have informed our recommendations outlined in the Executive Summary. In addition, it is worthwhile to highlight the following information.

The following were common across all international sites:

- All have made an investment in GPU hardware.
- All are seeing a steep increase in adoption of ML.
- Access to big annotated datasets is expensive and scarce, specifically with the privacy concerns.
- All face skill shortages due to the lucrative offerings in the industry but consider attracting and retaining staff critical

Many have:

- Tried commercial cloud but consider cost and lack of integration to be major issues.
- Seeking active collaborations to train models across different sites in order to access larger and diverse datasets, and also to assist in circumstances where data cannot move between jurisdictions.
- Consider it a priority to democratise AI, by providing naive users and researchers with pre-trained models, tools, etc. specific to their domain.
- Invest in training and development activities.
- Invest in programs to build community, develop self education materials and events such as symposium and hackathons.

5. Analysis and/or Emerging Themes

5.1 Classifying ML Researchers

Based on the survey outcomes, the ML researchers can be broadly classified into two different cohorts

- researchers who develop new ML algorithms & techniques & apply them to their research
- researchers who are applying existing ML algorithms to their research

Fig 5.1.1 ML Research cohorts

90% of the researchers who develop as well as apply ML to their research are multidisciplinary and have active collaborations. These researchers collaborate with researchers from other fields of research to have access to real datasets and solve real and practical research questions that has social impact.

This cohort classification characterises their field of research, technology & tools they use, techniques they apply, challenges they face, their skills & expertise and their requirements for future.

5.1.1 Field of research

Understandably, Information & Computing Sciences and Engineering have been the dominant field of research among both the cohort of researchers.

Medical and Health Sciences (19.8%) discipline is the highest in applying ML algorithms to their research followed by Biological sciences (6.2%), Mathematical sciences (6.2%) and Earth Sciences (4.9%).

Mathematics sciences (8.6%), Commerce, Management, Tourism & services(5.2%) followed by Economics, Biological Sciences, Physical Sciences and Earth Sciences(3.4% each) are found to be both developing and applying algorithms to their research.

Fig 5.1.2 Cohorts by field of research

Graph doesn't include Information and computing sciences.

5.1.2 Expertise

68% of the researchers with expert ML skills develop algorithms and apply existing algorithms to their research, whereas 67% of the researchers with intermediate ML skills focus more on applying existing ML algorithms to their research.

5.1.3 Techniques

79% of the researchers use Neural networks and deep learning in their research. A whopping 93% of the researchers apply deep learning to their research and 52% develop new deep learning algorithms

5.1.4 Proportion of time

Cohort of researchers who apply existing ML algorithms for their research are spending almost equal efforts on data pre-processing and model generation activities, whereas, the other cohort is spending significantly higher proportion of their time (42%) on model development activities.

Fig 5.1.3 Proportion of time spent by different cohorts

5.1.5 Challenges

Most respondents indicated that their **compute needs will increase by 150%-200% over the coming year.**

Current computing capacity is highly inadequate with requirements growing quickly.

- 68% of the researchers expect that their compute needs to grow by 100%-200% in the next year. 15% expect that their computing needs will grow by over 200%.
- 54% of the researchers indicate that compute capacity is their major challenge.

5.2 Emerging Themes

5.2.1 Big Data & Sensitivity

It is evident that researchers are processing and analysing variety of *data in the magnitude of terabytes*, specifically, images, audio & videos, 3D structures, genomic sequencing and geo-spatial data.

When Big Data ≠ Enough Quality Data: Following are the key challenges that the researchers are facing with the data

- Lack of sufficient high quality data
- Long and time consuming data capture, cleanup & management activities
- Huge manual efforts required for annotating and labelling data to use for training models

Data collection and Data preprocessing together takes at least 40% of the researcher time and 63.24% of researchers want to develop their data management, cleanup and transformation skills in the future.

Fig 5.2.1 Average time spent in various stages for ML.

Public benchmarking datasets & need for more open Research Data: ML researchers (73%) are found to use public data collections for their research in order to overcome the challenges around availability and accessibility of quality research data. Some public data collections come with free and open license, while some are paid and restricted sharing licenses. **UK Biobank data, Open street maps and social media usage data** are few popular ones.

Data Sensitivity & privacy is trending: Sensitivity of the data and the intricacies associated with sharing and handling sensitive data has emerged as the most complex challenge among the ML research, specifically in a certain field of research like Medical and Health sciences. 57% of the researchers have indicated that their data is sensitive. **Personal identifiable information, Patient health data, Defense data, Industry IP protected data, Animal research data and Policies related data** are the significant categories of sensitive research data.

<p>Key challenges identified in handling sensitive data are</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • De-identification process is not fool proof and can be potentially re-identified • Data sharing agreements are complex • Privacy, ethical and legal issues arising out of handling sensitive data • Regulatory frameworks like GDPR
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Table 5.2.2 Challenges of handling sensitive data

5.2.2 Computing Capacity

Of the research groups responding to our survey 44 were able to estimate their GPU usage, or their usage was calculated from known project allocations on MASSIVE, Wiener or the research cloud. We normalised these responses and extrapolated them across the three participating Universities, and the Australian Go8 Universities.

GPU Usage by Respondents to the survey		
Respondents reporting or estimating their GPU usage	42	projects
Total GPU hours by these respondents	987,263	GPU hours
Size of GPU cluster required to accomodate	125	GPUs
(Assumes 90% availability)		
Extrapolation across entire survey cohort of 128 research groups identified across participating Universities		
Total projects	128	projects
Total GPU hours by these respondents	3,008,802	GPU hours
Size of GPU cluster required to accomodate	382	GPUs
Extrapolation across Australian Go8		
(Assumes the three participating Universities are a representative sample of the Australian Go8 - they are representative of 3 of the 8)		
Total projects	341	projects
Total GPU hours by these respondents	8,023,471	GPU hours
Size of GPU cluster required to accomodate	1,018	GPUs

ML researchers largely use HPC/Research cloud environment and local desktops for their compute needs. 49% of the researchers are using the HPC and research cloud environments and 35% of them use Local desktop.

Most of the researchers (47%) access to their GPU needs through a scheduler at an HPC facility. Other popular GPU access mechanisms are local desktop and interactive access.

68% of researchers were concerned about either their current accessible compute capacity or future accessible capacity.

Fig 5.2.3 Compute capacity requirements.

Bigger the data, larger the compute: Almost 75% of researchers surveyed indicated that the key challenge in accessing compute is *not having enough GPU capacity, leading to use of CPUs instead of GPUs, long waiting time, difficult allocation processes*

Compute needs vary in-line with expertise of the researchers: 50% of experts say that their compute requirements are not met and 32% are concerned about their future needs. Researchers with Intermediate ML skills indicate that their requirements are met currently but they are equally concerned that their needs might not be met in the future.

68% of experts & 52% of intermediates think that their compute requirements are going to grow more than 150% over the coming year

Capacity and efficiency of use are the key: Having access to sufficient and appropriate compute capacity is the major constraint highlighted by the researchers. A large number of cohort also highlighted the necessity to have more awareness, training and efficiency measures for using the available toolkit efficiently.

Fig 5.2.4 Challenges in accessing compute

5.2.3 Skills

Machine learning skills with domain expertise is seen as one of the key challenges in applying Machine learning to research. One of the researchers interviewed highlighted that **“lack of physical, chemical and material expertise, but having considerable machine learning experience hasn’t proved to be effective”**, since the Machine learning expert couldn’t understand the research problem well. Hence researcher focus on ensuring their entire research group are proficient in ML

Fig 5.2.5 ML expertise of entire research group

Training needs are found to be different for different cohorts.

Cohorts applying ML are found to be more interested in improving their skills on training the models and using HPC efficiently. On the other hand, cohorts developing and applying ML are looking to improve their skills on theoretical aspects of machine learning.

Fig 5.2.7 Training needs for different cohorts

Fig 5.2.6 Training needs by expertise

5.3 Challenges

While Availability of quality big data, Accessibility of GPUs & high speed storage and ML skills with domain expertise are significant challenges the ML researchers currently face, It is evident that the future challenges are going to be much beyond.

1. Training ML models requires big data but big quality data comes with following challenges
 - a. Privacy, ethical and legal issues pose challenges to accessibility of existing quality annotated data within different institutions
 - b. Annotating and labelling new datasets is expensive and time consuming, since it requires trained experts in the field to manually inspect and label the data
2. Applying AI and ML for social good
 - a. Explainability and Bias associated with training and scaling models
 - b. Data needed for social impact use cases like improving healthcare are not easily accessible
3. Applicability of theoretical AI & ML concepts to research
4. Training and retaining skilled staff in a competitive market with higher Industry benefits
5. Lack of collaborations and co-ordinated efforts within and across Institutions

Table 5.3 Future challenges in applying ML

5.4 Commercial Cloud Points Raised by Respondents

19% of respondents indicated that they have now or in the past used commercial cloud for ML. Key discussion points raised in questions regarding commercial cloud are as follows.

AWS and Azure are most commonly used.

Key advantages of commercial cloud highlighted:

- Quick access
- Support from vendors
- Cloud credits for research
- Availability of pre-trained models like object detection models.

Key challenges of commercial cloud highlighted:

- Very expensive to scale
- Memory not sufficient most of the time
- Scheduling is manual
- Setup process is complex & error messages are meaningless
- Short term free credits is not worth the effort of moving data and setting up models, since it is time consuming
- Suitable only for publicly available datasets, not suitable for sensitive data due to ethics requirements & efforts in redacting the data